

Improvement of special physical training of karate athletes at the initial training stage

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Abstract

Purpose: Development of proposals and recommendations for the organization of the planned training process for improving the special physical training of karate athletes at the initial training stage.

Methods: analysis of domestic and foreign literature and data of sports practice, pedagogical observation, timing and testing of training and competitive loads according to pulsometry data, methods of testing and control exercises, competitions, pedagogical experiment, methods of mathematical statistics.

Results: According to the results of the training process in the 6-month mesocycle of karate athletes at the initial training stage, the physical fitness of the karate athletes of the control and experimental groups in the 30 m run before the study was 5.0 ± 0.04 sec. in the CG and 4.9 ± 0.04 sec. in the EG. At the end of the 6-month study, the 30 m run was equal to 4.6 ± 0.04 in the CG and 4.5 ± 0.05 in the EG. If there are indicators of special training, then before the experiment, after 3 months of study, the hand punches in CG were equal to 5.67 ± 1.04 and in EG 6.07 ± 1.07 , leg punches in CG 4.53 ± 1.03 and in EG 4.87 ± 1.06 .

Conclusion: Special physical training should include means for the comprehensive development of a karateka. Therefore, the ability of karate practitioners at the initial training stage, that is, the development of striking technique, is an important component of special training in combat sports. At the same time, the basis for the implementation of this component is the improvement of special physical training of karateka during the 6-month mesocycle training period.

Keywords: special physical training, technical training, mesocycle period, karate WKF, special exercises, competitive training.

Introduction

The goal of our country's karate WKF sports system is the preparation of athletes for sports competitions, aimed at achieving the highest level of training for this athlete, based on the specifics of competitive activity and guaranteeing the achievement of planned sports results. Therefore, improving the motor abilities and functional capabilities of the body during exercises in karate constitutes the successful performance of the competitive activity of the sport and the necessary level of special psychological training.

In the system of long-term training, great importance is attached to the preparation of children and adolescents for sports. When engaging children and adolescents in sports, the goal is achieved if the teacher-coach considers and organizes it as a pedagogical system consisting of many interconnected components aimed at achieving a high level of sports (physical) perfection.

The formation of science about the system of training young athletes is carried out in several stages: from the study of specific issues to major scientific works that reveal sports training and related major scientific achievements, to the introduction of scientific achievements into practical activities. Currently, the following sections of training young athletes are very well developed: methods of age-related development of physical qualities; a system for forming long-term training for young athletes; the diet and structure of training loads; a system for selecting young athletes; methods of comprehensive monitoring of the preparedness of students of sports schools; organizational and methodological foundations of youth sports.

The initial training stage, the main goal of which is to strengthen the health of young athletes, comprehensive physical training, and mastering the basics of technique. The main tools of this stage are general developmental and special exercises, outdoor games, exercises for the development of basic physical qualities, and the creation of a technical school for the chosen sport.

In our republic, great attention is paid to the development of children's sports on a scientific basis. "Wide involvement of youth in sports and selection of talented athletes from among them, formation of national teams with skilled athletes who ensure high results in sports" is of great importance. It should be noted that the problem of young karateka's failure to consistently achieve high results in prestigious international competitions is one of the priority tasks.

Based on the research conducted to eliminate these problems, as well as through the analysis of modern competitions, it was established that the introduction of complex combat tactical actions into the training process has a positive effect on increasing the effectiveness of the system of preparing karateka for major prestigious competitions. Also, the study of scientific works based on the results of research conducted in recent years shows the need for scientific substantiation by identifying and implementing in training effective means and methods that contribute to improving the special technical training of karate athletes at the initial training stage.

In many sports, the initial training stage lasts from one to three years. The minimum age of those involved in the initial training stage depends on the specifics of the chosen sport. Including the initial training stage, it is recommended to involve karate athletes from the age of 10.

Results and discussion

The main goal of organizing the sports training process at the initial training stage is to ensure conditions for broad, fundamental training of the student, especially in cases where the specialization begins in adolescence and earlier.

The distribution of the ratio of training time for different types of training in karate depends on the specifics of the sport. The factor determining the rational allocation of time is the need to master the technical elements of sports. Karate WKF is a sport that requires mastering a large arsenal of technical elements. Therefore, according to many authors, from 30 to 60% of training time is allocated for mastering sports techniques in various martial arts in the annual cycle.

Currently, many specialists emphasize the need for the targeted development of special physical qualities and abilities, which directly determine the success of karate in the chosen sport at the initial stage of training, and the creation of conditions for subsequent successful specialization.

According to L.V. Volkov, at the initial stage of training, it is recommended to reduce the volume of physical activity by increasing exercises aimed at mastering the technique of movements. Performing such exercises at low and medium intensity provides the necessary physical training of young athletes.

In his scientific research, the winner of the 2021 World Karate WKF Championship,

M.D. Otabulayev, developed a methodology for teaching self-assessment of the effectiveness of karate athletes in preparing children at the initial stage of training for sports, taking into account selection and physical abilities. He also paid special attention to the fact that among young karateka there are athletes with high, medium, and low self-esteem.

To further study the problem, it is necessary to study the factors influencing the development of self-efficacy of young karateka, and according to the results of the analysis conducted during the development of this motivational tool, it has been proven that this tool has good results for use in karateka, therefore it can be used.

The possibility of young athletes participating in competitions is determined by the specifics of the sport and the existing regulatory documents. In many combat sports (karate, judo, wushu, taekwondo, sambo, and others), the participation of young athletes in official and unofficial competitions, as well as the implementation of mandatory programs in competitive mode, is ensured. This leads to the need to organize different stages, taking into account the preparatory periods.

In karate WKF, children aged 10 are involved in the initial preparatory stage, which lasts two to three years. The annual cycle consists of 52 training weeks, 6 of which can be held in the conditions of a sports camp. The ratio of training means depends on the specifics of sports science, the weight of technical training is significantly higher than that of representatives of other martial arts (from 30 to 50%), which is due to the abundance of competitive and special preparatory exercises, as well as the presence of practical training in practically all karate classes.

There are no unified norms of relations between preparatory departments, which is due to the insufficient scientific development of this problem and significant differences in the conduct of competitive activities in various programs of karate WKF. The number of training sessions in the weekly period is 2-3 days, and the break between classes does not exceed three days.

As a result of the special training program developed by us, the achievement of the research goal was carried out on the basis of 6-month pedagogical experience, and its goal was to improve special physical training through the use of training tools specific to karate.

Table 1. Planning of a 6-month special physical training process for athletes of the initial preparatory stage in karate WKF

Months	Field of training	Description
1 st month	Basic defensive and offensive actions	Straight strikes (gyaku-suki, kizami-suki), main blocks (age-uke, gedan-barai)
2 nd month	Maintain distance and move	Side and reverse movement (tai sabaqi), distance control, counter-attack
3 rd month	Single and combined attacks	Combinations of simple and two-to-three-strike attacks (suki + geri)
4 th month	Defense and Counter-offensive Techniques	Attacking after block, avoiding kicks (taisabaki)
5 th month	Work in real battle situations	Kumite practice, increasing reaction rate, developing reflexes and decision-making
6 th month	Test and competition preparation	Training fights, tactical games, special exercises aimed at increasing strength and speed

Athletes in the initial stage of training have a characteristic of rapid mastery compared to their age. Therefore, the aforementioned training processes are modified according to the coach's instructions, taking into account the physical preparedness of 10-year-old karate athletes.

When organizing the study, 10 children were taken for the control group and 10 children for the experimental group. A total of 20 young karateka participated in the study. For the control of physical indicators during the 6-month mesocycle of our scientific research, a

we rationally plan the training process, taking into account the general physical abilities of future karate athletes. During the training period, we will improve the mesocycle period of karate practitioners based on tables 1-2. It should be noted that, taking into account the process of development of skills and abilities of children in the initial period, a ticket is issued for participation in the championship of the sports school. The training process is improved by the coach depending on the growth rate of children's physical abilities.

After the end of the 3-month mesocycle

Table 2. Planning of a 1-day special physical training process for athletes of the initial preparatory stage in karate WKF

Stages of training process		Duration (min.)	Details
<i>Entrance (preparatory department)</i>	Physical training	15	Running, stretching, balance, and movement speed exercises
<i>Main part</i>	Protective techniques	15	Main blocks (age-uke, gedan-baray), escape (tai sabaqi) and distance control
	Attack combinations	20	Single and two-three-strike attacks (suki, geri, combined attacks)
	Counter-attacking technique	20	Counter-attack after defense, quick blocks after block
	Kumite (Extreme Battle)	10	Pair work, real combat, tactical approaches
Final part	Recovery stage	10	Muscle relaxation, breath control, stretching exercises

normative control test was taken on the general physical fitness of athletes (Table 3).

During the 6-month mesocycle of training for karate athletes at the initial stage of training,

training period, standards were taken for the control and experimental groups to determine their special physical fitness (Table 4). During the study, in particular, it was planned that the

Table 3. Indicators of general physical preparedness of karate athletes of the initial training stage in the control and experimental groups before the experiment

N	Indicators	X±m	
		EG	CG
1.	Run 30 m (sec)	EG	5,0±0,04
		CG	4,9±0,04
2.	60m Run (sec)	EG	13,2±0,05
		CG	13,2±0,05
3.	3x10 shuttle run (sec)	EG	10,6±0,04
		CG	10,7±0,04
4.	Long jump (cm)	EG	150,5±1,9
		CG	155,2±1,5

special physical condition and technical preparedness of karate athletes at the initial training stage will be at a high level during the 6-month training period, and after the end of the training period, a control test for special physical condition was taken (Table 4). Based on the research results, proposals and recommendations were developed.

karate athletes at the initial training stage. The reason is that during the initial preparation period, the athlete's correct mastery of the exercise and its improvement is of great importance. In our study, the final result of special physical training was as follows (Table 5).

Conclusion

Table 4. Indicators of special physical training of karate athletes of the initial training stage in the control and experimental groups for 3 months

№	Indicators	X±m	
		CG	EG
1.	Hand strike to gyaku-suki abdomen 10sec/time	CG	5.67±1.04
		EG	6.07±1.07
2.	Hand strike to kizami-suki head 10sec/time	CG	6.07±1.03
		EG	7.67±1.05
3.	Mavashi-geri kick 10sec/time	CG	4.53±1.03
		EG	4.87±1.06
4.	Foot Strike Roll-Geri 10sec/time	CG	4.12±1.07
		EG	5.27±1.09

In the process of improving the special physical training of karate athletes at the initial training stage, a 6-month mesocycle period was organized. In particular, during the study, much attention was paid to the technical training of

In improving the special physical training of karate athletes at the initial stage of training, the half-year mesocycle period was effectively

Table 5. Indicators of general physical fitness of karate athletes of the initial training stage in the control and experimental groups

N	Indicators	X±m	
		EG	CG
1.	Run 30 m (sec)	EG	4,6±0,04
		CG	4,5±0,05
2.	60m Run (sec)	EG	10,3±0,1
		CG	10,0±0,1
3.	3x10 shuttle run (sec)	EG	9,0±0,07
		CG	8,8±0,06
4.	Long jump (cm)	EG	170,1±1,4
		CG	177,4±1,9

Table 6. Indicators of special physical preparedness of karate athletes of the initial training stage in the control and experimental groups

№	Indicators	X±m	
		CG	EG
1.	Hand strike to gyaku-suki abdomen 10sec/time	CG	6.12±1.14
		EG	7.07±1.37
2.	Hand strike to kizami-suki head 10sec/time	CG	7.24±1.53
		EG	8.07±1.75
3.	Mavashi-geri kick 10sec/time	CG	5.43±1.63
		EG	6.26±1.56
4.	Foot Strike Roll-Geri 10sec/time	CG	5.67±1.37
		EG	6.48±1.65

organized to improve motor skills adapted to the competitive process.

When improving the technical training of karate athletes at the initial training stage, skills were developed to eliminate mistakes and shortcomings, taking into account 3-month special physical training.

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